

ازدواجی زندگی کے اصول اور اس کے مسائل کا حل اسوہ رسول ﷺ کی روشنی میں

THE PRINCIPLES OF MARITAL LIFE & RESOLVING MARITAL ISSUES
IN THE LIGHT OF PROPHET'S ﷺ LIFE**Muhammad Mubashir Khan (ORCID ID: 0000-0003-3422-710X)**

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ABSTRACT

In Quran Allah Says: And among his signs is this, that he created for you mates from among yourselves, that you may dwell in tranquility with them, and he has put love and mercy between your (hearts).

But in our society, we see a totally opposite picture. After getting married within a few months married couple started arguing on small matters and clear sign of agitation and distress can be seen in their lives. Why it is happening in our society can be understood if we take a closer look into the prophet w marital life.

In this article we have broken down this subject into two steps. **First**, what were the principles the prophet of Allah w had developed for dealing with his wives. **Second**, being human whenever any sort of challenges were raised by his wives, how the Prophet of Allah w dealt with them.

Keywords: Marital life, Seerat, Wives of the Prophet PBUH, Marital Issues.

کلیدی الفاظ: ازدواجی زندگی، سیرت، ازواج مطہرات، ازدواجی مسائل۔

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